

Speed in Lorentz Transformation Directly Linked to Increased Momentum Hence Impulse? Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 22, 2025

The Lorentz transformation seems to be traditionally seen as an extension of the Galilean transformation. The Galilean transformation, in turn, focuses on how the velocity of a particle with rest mass is changed when seen by a viewer in a moving frame. In Part I, we argued that a Lorentz transformation pertains to interactions, i.e. momentum and impulses, and so one is ultimately interested in how $-v$ (speed of a moving frame) changes momentum and not on how it changes perceived velocity. In other words, we argued that one does not need to think in terms of every velocity (i.e. the velocity of light) as changing as seen from a moving frame.

Here, we give a second argument to support this viewpoint. We suggest a priori that the Lorentz transformation is strictly related to interactions and the change in p (momentum) associated with a moving frame. It is true that the speed of the moving frame needs to be measured by someone in the rest frame, but once that value is obtained, the question is: How does this speed affect momentum as seen in the moving frame? We suggest that one may experimentally and numerically obtain the Lorentz transformation directly as one which affects (pc, E) without any consideration of how (x, ct) transforms. In such a case, there is no surprise that the speed of light is the same as seen in all frames as this has nothing to do with momentum (hence impulse) changes described by the derived Lorentz transformation. In other words, we argue that the Lorentz transformation may be seen as fundamentally an interaction transformation. (This idea then even holds when it is applied to x, t for particles with rest mass and photons.)

Traditional Focus on Apparent Speeds as Seen From Moving Frames

As noted in Part I, the notion of relativity is that physical laws are the same in different frames moving with constant speed relative to each other, but such equations are ones of interaction. In Newtonian mechanics, there is the notion of a Galilean transformation, i.e. v of a particle in a rest frame, is $v + v_1$ (where $-v_1$ is the velocity of a moving frame). The particle presumably has rest mass. The focus is entirely on velocities and how they change when viewed from moving frames. This idea seems to be traditionally carried over into the generalized special relativistic Lorentz transformations. In fact, one may derive the Lorentz transformation strictly for x, ct transformations, where b is a parameter with units of speed which is the same in all frames.

One may use: m_0 rest mass at rest at $x=0, t$.

As seen from a moving frame $(-v)$: $x'/t' = v$. ((1))

((1)), together with: $xx - bbtt = x'x' - bbt't'$ is enough to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} &| g(v) \quad v/b \quad g(v) | \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \\ &| v/b \quad g(v) \quad g(v) | \end{aligned}$$

Insisting that $x/t=c$ and $x'/t' = c$ for a photon leads to $b=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum. The above arguments are strictly related to x,t space and give the impression that a Lorentz transformation is essentially a space-time one. In this note, we suggest that one may bypass this space-time viewpoint altogether and consider only interactions. This avoids any confusion as to why the speed of light of a photon is c in a rest frame, but also in a moving frame, we argue.

Obtaining the Lorentz Transformation Experimentally with Only Momentum Considerations

We suggested in Part I that interactions are key to the Lorentz transformation and these are linked to momentum, which in turn, is linked to impulse. We suggest the following. Imagine that there is a person in a rest frame who has a particle with rest mass, m_0 , and a set of photons with different momenta. This person may create physical targets such that they are first broken by a specific m_0, v_1 or a specific p of a photon.

Next, the person in the rest frame measures the speed of a moving frame ($-v$). The person in the moving frame thinks he/she is at rest and has a set of targets which are broken by various minimal momenta, whether from a rest mass (in the moving frame) or photon. In other words, two sets of targets are calibrated, one in the rest frame and the other in the moving, based on the minimum momentum which breaks them.

The person in the rest frame creates a set of mov_1, mov_2, mov_3 etc and photon momenta p_1, p_2, p_3 . The person in the moving frame interacts with these with his/her targets and finds that they do not correspond to those of the person in the rest frame. (I.e. the results of the person in the rest frame performing the same interaction experiment.) This suggests that the momenta as seen in the rest frame are not the same as those seen in the moving frame. The two frames are distinguished by a different velocity v . (In other words, there is communication between people in the two frames. A person in the rest frame states that he has a momentum p created in a certain way which breaks a certain target. The person in the moving frame has this same target (because he/she can create the same p in the moving frame, but then finds that the momentum of the particle in the rest frame breaks a different target when it interacts with a moving frame target.

At this point, the result is qualitative because although v is a number, momentum is not because there is no equation for it. It is only measured in terms of targets, but it is known that the momentum is different as seen in the moving frame. There is no notion here of augmenting speed. A person in the rest frame may measure the speed of light and a person in the moving frame perform the same measurement in his/her frame. The result is the same. Hence, differing frames is not about velocity (universally). It seems to be rather about momentum.

One may perform interference experiments with photons and use:

$$P = \hbar / \text{wavelength} \quad \text{where wavelength is determined experimentally.}((3))$$

\hbar is also known experimentally.

As a result, one may label each target by the minimal momentum number which breaks it. One may find that for particles with rest mass m_0 that $m_0 v$ is not momentum, but that there is an enhancement factor based on v . One might even be able to guess its form:

$$1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{It is not necessary to guess this mathematical form.})$$

More importantly, the person in the moving frame may do the same. In the case of different masses m_0, m_1, m_2 at rest in the rest frame, these will be seen to have the same p values as measured in the rest frame target experiments involving accelerating m_0, m_1, m_2 to speed v , when there is an interaction between m_0, m_1, m_2 . Furthermore, one may see how a photon with p in the rest frame has its p changed when colliding with a target in the moving frame. (The same holds for p (of a particle with rest mass) in the lab frame which collides with targets in the moving frame.)

If one assumes the equation $E=pc$ for a photon in the rest frame based on the wave equation $c=\text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$, then one knows E and p for each photon in the lab frame, but also E' and p' for each photon in the moving frame if one assumes that c is the same in both frames. In particular, a collision with a lab p photon yields a p_1 target measurement and one finds $E'=p_1 c$. Thus, one knows the mappings:

$$(pc, E) \text{ from the lab to } \longrightarrow (p'c, E') \text{ after a collision with a target in the moving frame} \quad ((4))$$

Now setting $c=1$ (for simplicity here), one has:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ q & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} |p| \\ |E| \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |p'| \\ |E'| \end{bmatrix} \quad ((5)) \quad \text{Here } a, b, q, d \text{ are unknown at first.}$$

For a photon with $c=1$, $p'=p$ and $E'=E$, so $a+b = q+d$. If $v=0$, the matrix in ((5)) is the identity, so b and q vanish. Given the measurements of p for particles with a rest mass in the lab frame, one knows the values of:

$$p = g(v) m_i v_i \text{ where } m_i \text{ is a certain rest mass and } v_i \text{ a certain speed.} \quad ((6))$$

Thus, b and q should be $-v g(v) D$ where D is the constant which converts m_i into an energy. (It may later be shown to be cc which is 1 using $c=1$.)

Also, by ((7)), $a=d$.

One knows p' (from a target hit with the moving frame) and p (from a target hit in the rest frame) so:

$$p' = (a+b) p = (a - v g(v)) p \quad ((8))$$

One may see that $g(v)$ is the value which enhances $m_i v_i$ ((6)). One may solve ((8)) for "a" and see that it yields:

$$a = g(v) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, one has all values of the matrix, although in numerical form. As noted, one may actually be able to guess the form $1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ from the numerical values, but either way, one has the Lorentz transformation for p, E based on experiment and does not have to consider any change in velocity due to a moving frame. This is the main point we wish to make. Thus, the Lorentz transformation may be seen as one which describes changes to interaction variables p and E and there is no real issue of whether the speed of a photon is still c even after seen by a moving frame ($-v$).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Galilean transformation is entirely based on the notion of a velocity in a moving frame being seen as a different velocity in the rest frame. This is not a notion of interaction. Furthermore, the Galilean transformation is not general. We argue, however, that one may obtain the general Lorentz transformation of x and t based on velocity considerations. For instance, for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t , one may impose $x'/t'=v$ and create the Lorentz transformation matrix with c (speed of light) replaced by some constant b . If one applies this matrix to a photon using $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$, one finds $b=c$. At this point one has the Lorentz transformation and there is no notion of p (momentum) or E , giving the impression that the Lorentz transformation is only linked with space-time. This leads to the physical issue of explaining why c is the same in any moving frame. In fact, it seems traditionally that this is imposed as an assumption. In the $x-t$ derivation of the Lorentz transformation, one has a b constant which is the same in all frames and has speed units. This immediately begs the question: Why does this not change according to a Galilean transformation?

Here, we suggest creating the Lorentz transformation experimentally, strictly for dealing with p (momentum) and E , i.e. interaction variables. In such a case, one does not need to think in terms of a Galilean transformation or for changes in speed as seen from a moving frame. There is no issue about c being the same in all frames because one is only focused on changes of p and E .

By using $\hbar/\text{wavelength} = p$ for a photon, one may find the numerical value of p for a range of photons as seen in the lab frame. One may also create a set of targets labeled by the minimal photon p which breaks them. One then finds that the minimal rest mass momentum which breaks them is not mv , but $mv g(v)$ and has the set of $g(v)$ values as well. We show that a person in a frame moving with $-v$ relative to the rest frame may also have such a set of targets calibrated in the moving frame. Then, when photons from the rest frame collide with targets in the moving frame, one sees that the targets which are broken are not p ones, but p' ones. We then show how one may numerically derive the full Lorentz transformation from this experiment. Thus, we obtain the Lorentz transformation experimentally for p and E alone and do not have to worry whether c is the same in one frame as in another. It is assumed that it is and this may be experimentally verified by a person measuring c in both the rest and moving frames. The point is that the Lorentz transformation is now seen exclusively as one describing changes in p and E , interaction variables. There is no puzzle as to why a photon should have the same speed in all

frames (at least from the point of view of the Lorentz transformation) if one is only interested in the Lorentz transformation describing E, p changes in frames with different $-v$, i.e. interaction considerations.